

Original article

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TRENDS IN THE APPLICATION OF SOFT ROBOTIC GLOVE IN THE REHABILITATION OF STROKE PATIENTS IN THE REPUBLIC OF SERBIA

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Abstract: *A soft robotic glove (smart glove) in modern medicine, in the field of rehabilitation, is a revolutionary device that can successfully restore the function of the hand and fingers during the rehabilitation process. The device is widely used in the world, while in Serbia, it is not widely used. The aim of the work was to show patients with hand-to-finger dysfunction the possibility of alleviating their problems by using a smart glove. Approaching the possibility of wearing a glove was done through the education of randomly selected patients. The education consisted of showing tutorials from the Internet with the necessary clarifications. After the education, the patients expressed their opinion through an interview, which can be generalized in the statement that the information was very useful to them and that they understood that they could benefit from the glove in the form of an improvement in their health condition. Patient education played a significant role in patients' willingness to accept the possibility of using a soft robotic glove.*

Keywords: *Patient education, soft computing, soft robotic glove, rehabilitation, stroke.*